

Comparison of different diagnostic methods for the detection of *Enteromyxum leei* (Myxozoa) in farmed gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*)

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INTRODUCTION

Enteromyxum leei is an enteric Myxozoan parasite causing the so-called “razor blade syndrome” in gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*), a chronic condition characterized by a progressive weight loss up to emaciation in adult fish. Currently no treatments are found to be effective against this parasite, but a recent experimental study showed promising results using a functional feed for mitigating enteromyxosis (Palenzuela et al., 2020. *Dis. Aquat. Org.*, 138, 111–120). During a field trial aimed to confirm the efficacy of this functional feed in an Italian sea bream facility where enteromyxosis was already known to be present, different methods for the detection of *E. leei* were compared to establish the more reliable diagnostic test also in relation to a non-lethal approach.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

During the aforementioned field trial, different methods were applied to detect *E. leei*: microscopical observation of a drop of intestinal content collected by squeezing the anus followed by 100 random observations per slide (400× magnification) and count of parasitic stages/field; rectal sample collected by probing the rectum with a cotton swab and subjected to qPCR (Piazzon et al., 2017. *Microbiome*, 5(1), 164); histological observation of portions of rectal ampulla from the same fish subjected to microscopical examination and qPCR.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The comparison of the different diagnostic methods applied confirmed the qPCR as the most reliable and sensitive method for detecting the presence of the parasite, offering also a semiquantitative estimation of the infection intensity based on the cycle threshold (ct). The microscopical observation, despite being easily feasible, costless and reliable to detect *E. leei* in advanced course of infection, can show difficulties in detecting early developmental stages and estimating low infection intensities when compared to qPCR. Histology appears to be a useful complement to qPCR and microscopical observation in assessing pathological alterations due to *E. leei* but shows underestimation issues with regard to the intensity of infection, also with false negative results. In fact, at histology developmental stages of *E. leei* have never been detected when the qPCR ct was ≥ 31 , even if the accepted ct threshold to consider a fish positive for *E. leei* is < 38 (Piazzon et al., 2017, *l.c.*). Furthermore, unlike histology, microscopical observation and qPCR can be performed on non-lethal samples collected from anesthetized fish. In conclusion, the use of qPCR could be the best option for the screening of newly introduced fish and to check the course of infection in farmed fish.

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